

THE PLASTICITY OF THE WORK OF HILAL SAMI HILAL: “YOUR SAMI” BLANKETS

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ABSTRACT

The present article seeks to weave an interartistic reflection on plasticity in the work “Seu Sami”, by the capixaba artist Hilal Sami Hilal, exhibited at the Vale Museum in 2007. For this purpose, the comparative image becomes evident as a basis of research, highlighting various points of view with relation to gestural, rhythmic and calligraphic aspects present in the artist's work. Entering the discussion of the abandonment of traditional support and the use and appropriation of other support as a basis for creation and maturation in the creative process, approaching the concepts of Time, Matter and Memory from the philosophers of Henri Bergson and Didi-Huberman.

Keywords: Interartistic, plasticity, Hilal Sami Hilal, Henri Bergson and Didi-Huberman.

INTRODUCTION

Some artists from the *80's Generation* extended their pictorial experimentation by appropriating various raw materials, going beyond the traditional field, permeating conceptual

ideas. In this sense, art often approaches a *philosophical act*. The field of philosophy is primordial in the relations and conceptions that broaden the subjectivities of plastic ideas. The concept of an *expanded idea* permeates subjects that go beyond the pictorial plane of tradition. In order to understand and relate the conceptions of art and philosophy, we will approach the relations between *Matter and Memory*, concepts of *Images-memory* related to *Transitory Time*, based on the philosophical concepts of Henri Bergson and Didi-Huberman. Dialoguing with the different subjects that guide Hilal's experiments, however, seeking to highlight the set of aesthetic, poetic, philosophical phenomena, relating to interartistic ideas and their creation process.

Hilal transits through various supports and languages with the intention of giving form to her concerns and experiments. To understand his poetics, it is necessary to understand some precepts he used, highlighting the deconstruction of the support and appropriation of non-traditional raw material, in this case, the support also appears as painting (paper paste with pigment).

The work, *Seu Sami*, was part of the exhibition that bears the same name, “Seu Sami” by the plastic artist Hilal Sami Hilal, held in 2007 at Museu Vale ⁴. In this exhibition, a series of works developed with handmade paper techniques and ferrous material were presented. Two raw materials with totally different aspects, however much used by the artist and transformed into objects and installations that question us. One with all its rigidity, transforms itself into such delicate pieces and another matter with its flexible and delicate molding, creating objects with such firm and rigid concepts.

For better understanding and contextualization this research seeks to weave reflections comparative and interartistic comparisons between the work *Seu Sami* and the structural anatomy of a cerebral *neural network*, that is, a network of neurons. Weaving a semiotic interrelationship between the anatomically organic forms of both examples. This relationship between a work of art and a physical/anatomical form of something non-artistic will certainly not be an easy task, as we are used to working with comparative aesthetics or an intersemiotic translation based on comparisons and different meanings, however, not so distant. . Research carried out in this field is usually linked by a close matrix, as an example between visual arts and music.

⁴The Vale Museum is housed in the former Pedro Nolasco Railway Station, on the shores of Vitória Bay (ES), in a typically industrial and port area in the municipality of Vila Velha, ES. Opened on October 15, 1998. Source: <https://museuvale.com/paginas/3>. Accessed on December 26, 2019.

In this article, we will discuss the interconnections of an object with a non-object. For this assumption, the reflections and arguments regarding the relations on the ' contemporary interarts ' will be relevant for us to understand the representations, combinations , fusion of codes and the intersemiotic ⁵translation of the image.

THE FACTORY EXPERIENCE: THE SUPPORT/PAINTING

“I didn't need to leave my poetry. I deal with paper derived from cotton rags. The paper comes from the clothes [...]. My work has the memory of the body. This heritage is very strong in my production” (Hilal Sami Hilal, 2007).

Descendant of a Syrian family, Hilal Sami Hilal , was born in the city of Vitória (ES), in 1952. In the 1970s, he began his degree in Visual Arts at the Federal University of Espírito Santo. Soon after, he started to dedicate himself to the academic area and taught for 20 (twenty) years in the Department of Arts at the same university, where he founded the chair of *Paper Studies* . In addition to *handmade paper* , he also taught *drawing, engraving, painting* and others.

The artist transits through various supports and languages to give form to his concerns and plastic experiments, raising questions, among them the practice of appropriating objects (family members' clothes as part of the recipe for handmade paper) in the poetic process. Thus, it is observed that this appropriation is impregnated with memory and maturation, full of the experience of a time that is transitory and reinvented as a support/painting. At this moment, epistemological relations with the concept of an *expanded idea of art emerge* which becomes necessary to understand the articulation process of the artist's poetic thought and action, a situation already widely possible to be seen in his productions with paper.

Other contemporary artists from the post-1980s generation, including Carlos Vergara, Daniel Senise, José Bechara and others, began their plastic experiments with unusual raw materials. Using *in natura ores*, fiber, appropriation of alien objects and impalpable *things* , however loaded with meanings, such as *transitory time and memory* . Matter and concepts

⁵ Intersemiotic translation, also called interarts translation, consists of the transposition of a system of signs to another . It is a movement and process that paradoxically equates meanings through a different sign system, that is, intersemiotic translation recognizes the specificity of the various semiotic languages (painting, literature, theater, photography, cinema, television) and at the same time welcomes the exchange between them in a process of creative transcoding. Source: AZERÊDO, Genilda; SANTOS, Eveline Alvares dos. Intersemiotic translation. In: *Abstracts of the IV National Meeting of Culture and Translation (ENCULT): Revolution, Translation and Revolutionary Translations*. v. 4 no. 1 (2017). João Pessoa: UFP, 2017.

began to interest the artists of this generation, who initiated another type of inspiration and creation.

Hilal perfected papermaking techniques from his travel experiences in Japan. The artist made two trips to the eastern country in search of knowledge of the art of making paper. The ritual and technique of making the fiber further marked his trajectory in the use of “the millenary practices of handmade paper” [...] (MENDES, 2008, p. 91), making this practice the experimental basis for his poetic process. After some research, trials and tests, Hilal developed a new formulation for the dough, starting in the 1990s with lacework on handmade paper.

The relationship with materials and craftsmanship has been developed over three decades by the artist, from which he began to build his own raw material, that is, his work material, and since the beginning of his career he has been developing experiments with role in his works. After some tests on the recipe and improved techniques, today he feels comfortable in his productions. Experimentations gave way to productions full of signifiers weaving plastic issues, aesthetics and philosophical concepts that permeate between issues related to Time, Matter and Memory. This manufacturing process is loaded with affective memory. This affectivity is remarkable in his poetics, which reflects in the plasticity of the objects produced by the artist and that are, directly and/or indirectly, related to the paternal bond, to memory, to the roots of culture and to matter itself.

Hilal may seek, through a set of actions, something that will emerge from plastic experimentation as an artistic practice, interweaving combination, appropriation, intervention and accumulation of memories, as philosophical ideas.

The paper pulp, made with cotton, organza or linen rags collected from the clothes of family members, bears the marks of time, the wear and tear of the fiber, fruits of the use and course of human experience, and all the accidents that have left their marks there. memories that will inevitably be incorporated into the work. “These rags are broken into a series of strips, mixed with glue, powdered PVA and water [...] liquefied, forming a fluffy paste [...]” (HERKENHOFF, 2008, p. 91).

Hilal adds pigments and carboxymethylcellulose ⁶to the paper mass, making the paste firmer and more resistant, making it possible for the artist to work on his gestures and draw with the aid of a pastry tube directly on the floor. “As it dries, the mass transforms into lacework,

⁶ Substance derived from cellulose by replacing the -OH groups with -CH₂CO₂Na as a thickener, stabilizer and in detergents, adhesives, emulsions, paints, food, cosmetics, oil drilling muds, etc. [acronym: CMC]. Source: FUJIMOTO, Juliana; REIS, Eduardo Alexandre de Oliveira; PETRI, Denise FS *Multilayer formation of polysaccharides and protein*, 2002. Accessed on December 26, 2019.

hollowed-out blankets and writing peculiar to its gestures. The act of detaching it from the ground configures itself as an extension of its own body: support and work at the same time” (HERKENHOFF, 2008, p. 92).

Figure 01: Hilal Sami Hilal, lace, s/d

Source : <http://galeriamariliarazuk.com.br/artistas/hilal-sami-hilal/biografia>
Accessed on 10/12/2019

Figure 01 portrays the gesture deposited by the artist, in which the paper is his writing and not just its support. It is your body, not your vessel. “The main issue of making is the possibility of uniting the gesture: the calligraphy/text to the matter. Communion happens directly” (HERKENHOFF, 2008, p. 38).

The universe of production of this artist is based on the relationship with materiality. Hilal became an experimental artist, intensifying his paper research, leveraging the possibility of new meanings and languages to express himself. “In his shed/studio, he researches materials, testing their resistance, discovering new effects, inventing other ways of doing things and creating new languages to express himself” (RAMALDES, 2015, p. 69).

Random, gestural, and calligraphic symbols gained space by moving away from the support position, giving other meanings. The “mantles” of the *Seu Sami installation* are like connected networks, between firm lines, without knowing where this gestural dance of connections begins and ends. Extrapolating the intersemiotic subjective translation not only of plasticity, but of the subjectivity of the artist's poetic process, can we point out that family affective ties would be intertwined with the idea of “plastic connections” visible in the composition of the work, *Seu Sami*?

What prevails for Hilal Sami Hilal are the memories that materialize in a diary: paper is the guiding thread for the making of these objects, so personal and delicate that they assume a permanent character in his works. Such incursions remain in the record of experience [...] (HERKENHOFF, 2008, p. 92).

The art critic and curator, Aracy Amaral “took to call her works material-work” (AMARAL, 2010, p. 185). In this sense, Herkenhoff (2008, p. 40) also referred to “Hilal's work as Bachelardian”, referring to Gaston Bachelard (1884-1962):

Philosopher of daydreams between the worker (the one who operates) and the matters with which he deals. Thus, in our view, due to the strength of the involvement with the substances in the construction of the works, thinking about Hilal's poetics necessarily involves analyzing his creative process. His trajectory is based on experiences with materials (RAMALDES, 2015, p. 70).

Contextualizing the use of different materials that guide Hilal Sami Hilal's experiments, seen in his creation process, we come across the *expanded idea of art* through the concepts of deconstruction of painting in its constituent elements and the appropriation of different supports, and at times sometimes the support itself is the painting, one part of the other, that is, support/painting.

In this experience of conjunction between the making of the support and the creation of the image (the work itself) Hilal perceived the “richness of the gestures” and the “freedom of construction of the object”. The work was granted at the same time that the paper support was manufactured. The creation of the 'material-work' was the solution to an old struggle for Hilal, within her creative process: the support/painting relationship. He stated that by solving this problem, his plastic research took off (RAMALDES, 2015, p. 82).

At the beginning of her experiments, it was only based on handmade paper, however, Hilal intensified new experiments and her interest in painting triggered the pigmentation of the paper pulp. His artistic process is composed from beginning to end by making from support to painting. Hilal developed all his gestures and “calligraphed” the floor like the North American artist Jackson Pollock (1912-1956), in which the gestural performance is his poetic process.

DRAWING AS A CREATIVE PROCESS

Seu Sami 's work goes beyond writing and the construction of a textual work itself. With calligraphic gestures, Hilal weaves textual plots that refer to the language system in which

Foucault refers to as “[...] an inextricable network of images and words [...]” (FOUCAULT, 1988, p. 50).

With regard to the work *Seu Sami*, we can point out that the writing of the drawing, the image/writing or linguistic signs and all calligraphic gestures are images that intertwine between support and writing, a cluster of lines that interconnect in information and accumulations causing a feeling of fulfillment and suddenly the *presence* of large empty spaces that are filled by the concept of absence. The images have a double character, they are drawing and writing at the same time, image and concept.

Foucault calls the system of *linguistic references* as being intellectual, as it leads to a syntactic reading of its signs. Still according to Foucault, the writings are interconnected with the drawings and this gesture transforms them into plastic elements. In consideration of these reflections, we can point out that Hilal's poetics is interested in visual aesthetics, transiting between plastic and intellectual aspects. Bringing as an element of language the intersection of symbols, traits, random and expressive gestures. Such elements are present in the visual totality of *Seu Sami 's blankets* .

A blanket with calligraphic arabesques [...] a grandiose installation of openings, shadows and mirrors as places of gaze, a letter wandering in space, everything deplores a lack. Geometric matter, written ornaments, words, and paper crafts come together as a semiotic flow in the flow of language. [...] 'The works are built with the most basic and fundamental of expressive elements: point, line, plane and space as support', warns the artist. Hilal Sami Hilal's semiology calls attention to the life of molded existential signs. In Hilal's symbolic fabric, there are no knots, but, according to him, intersections and encounters [...] and memory operations (HERKENHOFF, 2008, p. 53).

Some artists are not used to sketching in advance. However, analyzing figures 02 and 03, the record is present in Hilal's creative process. In which he develops this practice very well, which is part of the organization of thought in his creative process. Outlining his ideas and making relevant notes on the materials, measurements and other important technical data in the preparation of the works. The artist is in the habit of writing down projects from the beginning of the ideas to the setting up of the exhibition. The construction of his plastic thinking is clear.

The previous studies and prototypes, before and during the execution of their works, are called 'procedural documents.' The analysis of these records left by the artist can facilitate the understanding of the systems of signs that are articulated in the creation of the work. Also monitoring the production *in loco* , when possible, is another important aspect to understand the creative process. Observing the procedures in the atelier can contribute to the assessment of the relationships established between the artist's universe and his poetic project (RAMALDES, 2015, p. 70).

Figure: 02 - Sketch of the exhibition “Seu Sami”, Museu Vale.

Source: Seu Sami exhibition catalogue , 2008.

Figure 03: Sketch of the exhibition “Seu Sami”, Museu Vale.

Source: Seu Sami exhibition catalogue , 2008.

THE RELATIONS BETWEEN “TIME, MATTER AND MEMORY” IN POETIC DEVELOPMENTS

In the Bergsonian hypothesis, we live in temporality in which *time* is a process of past, present and future. According to Henri Bergson, the universe is an endless process, which engenders them and makes them disappear. And the process of life, being that, it is not eternal,

it is not fixed, but rather, a process of existing. And these transformations are precisely what is characteristic of *Time*, this power to make the original forms transcend what they are.

Evidently, the substance of our existence is *time* and *memory* acquires an extraordinary importance. We are beings much more of memory than of the present, we have much more past than present and, therefore, what reminds us is what constitutes us. Memory is what articulates and helps us understand the present, showing that *Time* is dependent on our past experiences.

From the point of view of human beings, *Time*, *temporality* and *Memory* constitute reality. For, “The past is in our present, as well as the future” (BORGES, 1989 p. 389). For Bergson, this conscience would have actions of similar proportion in relation to the past and the future. And the way memory acts in this process situates the present and the past, separated by a fine line. The Bergsonian thesis argues:

Let's say initially that if we place memory, that is, a survival of past images, these images will constantly mix with our perception of the present and may even replace it. For they are only conserved to become useful: at all times they complete the present experience by enriching it with the acquired experience and, as this one does not cease to grow, it will end up receiving and submerging the other (BERGSON, 1991, p. 49).

The conception of *time*, according to Didi-Huberman, corresponds to the 'phenomenological time' in which “the synthesis of the object that are founded in this unfolding of *Time* and [...] in that moment, therefore, the past dialogues in the pretense of a future, and from this dialectic, from this conflict, precisely arises the emerging present” (1998, p. 151).

Hilal dialogues with symbolic aspects, mainly linked to the idea of memory. These symbolic aspects run through the entire creative process, being visible in the making of the paper mass using old clothes from family and friends. The aesthetics of *Seu Sami's work* dialogues with lived experiences, perhaps related to that past, developing an approximation of an artistic work through philosophical work as a creative thought.

In contemporary philosophy, the term “representation” persists, but in some cases this philosophical idea adopts a second meaning for the image when it wants to accentuate the character and sensitive origin of the ideas or representations available to man.

[...] by 'image' we mean that a certain existence is more than what the idealist calls a representation, but less than what the realist calls a thing - an existence situated halfway between the 'thing' and the 'representation'. (BERGSON, 1991, p. 2).

The way in which Bergson treats the image coincides with the way in which many contemporary art theorists and philosophers have been referring to it. Henri Bergson, in *Matter and Memory* (1990), highlights important concepts that enhance the analysis of *Memory* and its relationship with *Image*. According to the author, *Memory* is a kind of conductor of the whole process. And in this process, the past and the present remain active, circumscribing the limits of our interpretation. Bergson called Memory *Images*. We can say that the experiences, wear and tear, the marks of temporality are *images* of a *memory*. Hilal, perhaps you are looking for such “image-memories”, not in the sense of creating, but something that will arise due to a set of actions, seeking to build a space impregnated with experiences and memories, coming from the rags of clothes with appropriation of materiality, bringing a support laden with temporal transience as a poetic process. The use of materials, appropriation, intervention, combinations, transforming the process into a relationship of dialogue with time and memory in the visual poetics of its materiality.

In the manufacture of handmade paper. Everything is crushed, creating a pasty mass that does not reveal any trace of the recognition that it was a piece of clothing, since the artist's purpose is not the visible recognition of a piece of textile rag when observing the work, but the idea of the concept of a *running time* with all the experience, wear and tear that the fabric carries and the idea of memory as part of *Seu Sami's plastic, gestural and poetic process*.

[...] Hilal's work is a celebration of doing. The physical action on the matter of the world implies impregnating his poetic objects with references from the history of art, psychic memory, the phenomenological study of doing (the dimensions of will according to Bachelard), theoretical aspects of psychoanalysis (with special interest in the thought of Lacan) [...]. Hilal's strong matter is the substratum of writing. If Hilal's work is *poiesis* of emptiness, *ipso facto*, matter cannot fill anything, but must take comfort in constituting only a physical notion of what is immaterial territory. This is the paradox of the work and “the matter begins to speak, not just to show itself” [...]. (HERKENHOFF, 2008, p. 92).

In Hilal's post-1990 visual-environmental speculations, we see that he begins to operate first, guided by memory-intuition, detaching himself from his concern with observing the real in front of him, and also driven by the fascination of chemistry in the transformation of the materials he handles. And with these processes, he establishes his personality with a contribution to our artistic milieu [...] (AMARAL, 2010, p. 189).

[...] Willing? Or are these extremely similar landscapes an obsessive and involuntary exercise in memory retention? According to Bergson, would

memory not be “habit memory or memory of repetition and representative memory? And the persistence of a state of mind cannot properly be considered as 'memory', but only its reappearance [...] the exercise of memory presupposes the retention of the remembered fact and its reminiscence. "The cause of both retention and reminiscence is the law of habit of the nervous system working in the association of ideas." [...] The artist working almost like a hand guided by memory, or memory and dream, as if in a waking state, disconnected from a justification or personal motivation. (AMARAL, 2010, p. 188).

AFFECTIVE RELATIONSHIPS: ABSENCE AND PRESENCE

The installation of *the Seu Sami exhibition* took place inside the 60-meter-long exhibition space at the Vale Museum in 2007, in Vila Velha (ES). At the ends of this span, eight blankets were installed, each measuring approximately 5.20 x 9.50 m and weighing 10 kg. Composed on each side of the wall and installed like large networks, with their wires connected, formed by voids, textures and gray gradations (like shadow in the mass). His calligraphic gestures and symbolic drawings are laden with “proposals” and subjectivity materialized in paper pulp. Some gestures come from the unconscious and resort to signs to define the openings of the *semiotic blankets* .

Composed of 'full and empty', the *Seu Sami installation* is highlighted by the drawings through the artist's gestures. The “emptiness” rests on a concrete support and allows the conclusion that its excellence is based on facing the unspeakable.

Hilal has materiality as the basis on which her work is based, her writings merge with matter creating the film-writing. His writings are not fixed on the plane, like graphisms generated by other material. On the contrary, the flat matter itself is transformed into texts that the artist draws “[...] on his planes, the lines that outline the elements are formed by the boundary between full and empty” (RAMALDES, 2015, p. 100) .

Hilal des ' work revolves around the *plastic-phantasmatic construction* of the figure of the imaginary father , the idealized one . Lacan (1985, p . 155). considers that “ the father's absence is a determining factor in the etiology of the subject's structure .” “ However , it is not up to critics to establish the etiology of the artist's psychic structure, but seeks to understand that he builds his work with empirical data from his experience, aesthetic, theoretical, formal elements and language materials ” (HERKENHOFF, 2008, p. 31).

In figure 04, the artist Hilal Sami Hilal covers himself with a blanket, which he shelters so zealously, being the “emptiness”, testimony of absence. His work, therefore, passes through the “emptiness of absence” (loss and lack), symbolized in the large surfaces of hollow

ornaments. It can be inferred that the work is the search for certification of the presence-absence of the father. Hanging from the walls, *Seu Sami*'s “blankets” are like a shelter in the void. The artist constructed a paradox and, at the same time, his work maintains the ontological purity of emptiness as such, and creates “support” from the very absence of the father. So emptiness is shelter itself.

Figure 04 : Photo of the cover of the “*Seu Sami*” catalogue. Valley Museum.

Source: *Seu Sami* exhibition catalogue , 2008.

“When I make lacework, I only find a mother. Dona Adélia made those roses. I am looking for the father, but I only find the mother. [...] the work is done around the lack. 'Absence manifests itself’”, concludes the artist (HERKENHOFF, 2008, p. 80).

What can be admitted that Hilal's work has a metalinguistic character, because it is intended for the discussion of his own identity is [...] "subject producer of an aesthetic factor and this subject is the artist who deals with his personal experience through means of its production” (LACAN, 1975, p. 160).

Figure 05 and 06 are images of the *Seu Sami* installation. Hilal emphasizes the “emptiness” of large areas discovered by the “absence of gestures” in *Seu Sami*'s sinuous lines . The meaning of the idea of “emptiness” and “absence” is perceptible in its plasticity, however the “presence of the absent father” emerges as another concept that goes beyond the visible materiality and inherent subjectivity of emptiness. According to Herkenhoff, “Hilal's strategy is not just the construction of layers of signifiers that can materially expose the father's absence in the form of art. By defining the very title of the exhibition, Hilal realizes the object, with high power of propagation and social inscription, of naming his father: *Seu Sami*” (2008, p. 33).

In this sense, it is inferred that “the work is in a field in motion, in which the conceptual and material elaboration of art does not unfold. Hilal understands that emptiness is absence” (idem, p. 26).

The materialization of the aesthetic sign is related to the artistic truth that concerns much more its insertion in its constitutive principle, that is, in its icon or *insight*, than its dependence on extra-artistic facts and realities. Their development capacity depends, after all, on “a mental capacity for insight and, of course, language awareness” (PLAZA, 2003, p.40).

In the language of poetry, [...] the mobility of senses and meanings correspond to the immobility of signs. [...] “The translator's starting point is not language in motion, the poet's raw material, but the fixed language of the poem” (PAZ, p. 15).

According to Plaza, “the character of poetry as an aesthetic sign, opens gaps for the inquiry about intersemiotic translation” (2003, p. 25). In the case of the poetic function, to create a resonance with it, the operations of information and aesthetic translation are fundamental . In this case, the artist is the poet of his plastic making. According to Santaella, in *Dialogismo* (1985), it is not our ego that gives meaning to language, but language that gives meaning to man . And it is in this intersection between what is said and what is heard that language and its established interpretive meanings are discovered. And this operation is common to creative translation, as we move and program the effects.

The absence of the father constitutes a flaw in the organization of the symbolic order. Perhaps, between the intersections of the narrated experience, the obscure field emerges. *Your Sami* is the place of this absence and now of the artist himself, being the space and projection of the imaginary, language and interpreting senses .

Figure 05 : Installation *Your Sami*: Hila Sami Hilal. Sao Paulo: Vale Museum.

Source: *Seu Sami* exhibition catalogue , 2008.

Figure 06: Installation Your Sami: Hila Sami Hilal. Sao Paulo: Vale Museum.

Source: *Seu Sami* exhibition catalogue , 2008

NEUROPLASTICITY IN THE WORK OF HILAL SAMI HILAL: THE BLANKETS OF “SEU SAMI”

Before talking about the aesthetics of an artistic installation, we will discuss what a *cerebral neural network* is ⁷and mainly its structural anatomy. It is a series of interconnected neurons . The means by which neurons interact with their neighbors usually consists of several axon terminals connected via a synapse to the dendrites of other neurons. If the sum of input signals exceeds a certain critical level, the neuron generates an action potential (AP), which is propagated along its axon, being transmitted, via chemical neurotransmitters or as an electrical signal, to other neurons. The neural cell or neuron constitutes the brain and the nervous system. It is responsible for thought beyond all our senses. Performs the function of communication and transmission of signals throughout the body.

From a brief analysis, we will begin the relations of images and the theory of symbolic forms through the comparison of the anatomical structures of a network of neurons and the work *Seu Sami* .

Neurons have similar characteristics and different functions, they vary only in the dimensions of each member: neurons have a nucleus, because they are a cell and it is surrounded by the or cell body, called the *Soma* . Neurons have small branches projecting from the *soma* (cell body). These branches outside the cell body are called *dendrites*, which tend to receive nerve stimuli. They receive and transmit signals. The neuronal cell has a tail called an *axon* that

⁷ Source: «The synapse». Khan Academy . Accessed on December 26, 2019.

can be very long or short. At the end of the *axons* are the *axon terminals*, which help connections with the *dendrites* feeding the network.

Estrutura anatômica de um Neurônio e algumas formas

Figura: 07

Figura: 08

Fonte: <<https://www.coladaweb.com/biologia/histologia/neuronios>>
Acesso em: 12 de outubro de 2019

Fonte: <https://planetabiologia.com/neuronio-estrutura-funcao-e-classificacao/>
Acesso em: 12 de outubro de 2019

The neuroplasticity, Also known as neuronal plasticity, it concerns the brain's ability to adapt throughout lived experiences. It is a characteristic of the nervous system that is essential for normalizing the performance of any activity that stimulates the brain, such as physical activity, reading or any learning process.

By definition, neuroplasticity is the ability of the nervous system, especially neurons, to adapt to changes in environmental conditions that occur in individuals' daily lives, a broad concept that extends from the response to destructive traumatic injuries to subtle ones . changes resulting from learning and memory processes ⁸.

A series of neurons or neural networks resembles a large network, with its wires interconnected. These branches of wires are known as *dendrites* , they facilitate the interrelationship between neurons. These neural networks are capable of composing all of our emotions, governing all of our behavioral and gestural senses. Scientific studies say that neurons have the ability to file experiences for indefinite periods in our memory, bringing back

⁸ Lent, Robert. One Hundred Billion Neurons: fundamental concepts of neuroscience. Neurons Transform: Biological Basis of Neuroplasticity. Sao Paulo: Ed. Atheneu, 2004, p. 134-63 .

remote memories. Such memories often arise through a simple fragrance or aroma, a taste, perhaps a gesture that reminds us of something sleeping in our mind or even a song, a movie, a stranger's face and the frequent comparisons with someone we know. Finally, the neurons or the neural network among several nervous functions have the ability to “keep”, either from the remote past or simply from the past/recent.

With an intersemiotic look at the factory object (*Seu Sami work*), we perceive through the comparative and imagery relationship that the anatomical structure of a set of interconnected neurons (neural network) with their *dendrites* , can be compared to the similarity of the plasticity of the work *Seu Sami* .

BIOLOGICAL NEURAL NETWORKS

Figura 9

Fonte: <<https://olhardigital.com.br/noticia/redes-neurais-estao-apanas-no-comeco-diz-microsoft/54378>> Acesso em: 12 de outubro de 2019

Figura 10

Fonte: <http://theconversation.com/brains-keep-temporary-molecular-records-before-making-a-lasting-memory-99731>
Acesso em: 21 de dezembro de 2019

Figura 11: Desenho de uma célula de Purkinje

Fonte: https://en.wikisource.org/wiki/File:PSM_V71_D110_Stained_purkinje_cell_from_a_human_cerebellum.png - Acesso em: 21 de dezembro de 2019

Returning to the image of figure 04, it shows the artist covered with a fragment of the work *Seu Sami*. This image brings the idea of a network with its connected lines, and assimilating this image with figure 11 (Drawing of a Purkinje cell), the *dendrites* resemble a network. In *Seu Sami*'s imagery language, the composition and gestures of the lines develop the idea of connection, a dialogue with the past and memory. It is not known when a line begins or ends, however, the aesthetic gesture is present in Hilal's lace blanket.

Hilal works with the plane horizontally on the floor. Your body sometimes inserts itself into the worked surface. For this artist, to the subjects he deals with, the body is fully present in the creative act. The hands in contact with the textures of the materials, the muscular strength in the clash with the resistance of the substances and the gaze building paths. The peculiarity of Hilal's work, the materiality, as well as his ways of operating point to the pleasurable bodily practice of his creative process (RAMALDES, 2015, pp. 95-96).

According to Freitas (*Choque entre forma*, 2016) [...] the similarities, *signatures* of things – leave their comfort zone to inhabit the core of experience. What distinguishes things from one another are not only their physical aspects [...] driven by the similarity that, through its web of similarities, follow paths, establish bonds, erect barriers and, finally, produce unique discoveries, poetic and aesthetic or new forms, autonomous and finalized, but still susceptible to new shocks, which can be understood, in a metaphorical context, as the encounter between neural networks and *Seu Sami*'s blankets.

The material form of *Seu Sami* starts with the composition of the paper pulp, the affective subjectivity. The dough is prepared from a “recipe of memories and a pinch of feelings” with explainable and inexplicable meanings through experiences that translate into a plastic and poetic form the absence of the father, who he lost as a child, bringing the longing for things not experienced in their childhood. These feelings between the past and the present are very intertwined in his artistic projects. Issues related to the “presence of emptiness” are relevant in his creations, whether on paper or ferrous material. And the relationship between “full and empty” in its construction, symbolically refers to the idea of the “presence of absence”.

Freitas (2016) seeks theoretical foundations on formativity and similarity with regard to subjects, through the philosopher's theories. Pareyson in *Aesthetics*: theory of formativity (1996) reports that the word *form* brings with it a considerable history of philosophical, aesthetic and psychological approaches. *Form*, in Pareyson, is not something distinct from content, nor is it an object in which symbolic dimensions are emphasized. The solution found

to avoid the most problematic connotations of the term, in addition to the option of naming the theory itself – “theory of formativity” and not “theory of form” – was to understand “form” as an organism. It is interesting to note that, like Dewey, Pareyson also sees similarity between artistic and non-artistic activities in terms of subjects and formative action.

Both thought and action, therefore, require productive strength and inventive capacity, since speculative and practical operations are constituted by a formative activity that, in the specific field, executes and produces the works at the same time that it invents the way in which they should be do (PAREYSON, 1996, p. 25).

According to Peirce,

Any thought is needed translation. When we think, we translate what we have in mind, be it images, feelings or conceptions (which, by the way, are already signs or quasi-signs) into other representations that also serve as signs, and [...] every thought is a translation of another thought, for any thought requires there to have been another thought for which it functions as an interpretant. We think in signs and with signs: “the only thought that can be known is the thought within signs as such, all thought is already inserted in the semiotic chain that tends to infinity (PEIRCE, 1977, p. 272).

For Peirce, wherever there is thought, it exists through sign mediation. Alexandre Freitas presents through the article *The shock between forms* (2016, p. 78) an affirmation to the comparative exercise of *images* [...] “declared or not in his poetics, very or little explicit in his works in the contact between forms and in the observation of the webs of similarities and differences”. This comparatist character between existences 'matter' or not, goes beyond the formal rules of intersemiotic translations, permeating through *subjective judgment*, through other conceptions, including personal and interpersonal experiences and translations of symbolic aspects between artist and spectator. In *Seu Sami*, in addition to plastic composition, the artist deposits his experiences on different levels: his losses, longing, memories that transcend the material character and objectivity of a translation.

If, at the level of “inner” thought, the semiotic chain is already established as an ideological translation process, what about that which is established in the exchange between broadcaster and receiver as a differentiated entity? In this case, the thought, which is already a sign, has to be translated into a concrete and material expression, [...] the language that allows communicative interaction. [...] the sign is the only reality capable of moving across the border between what we call the inner and outer world. To that extent, even the most “inner” thought, because it only exists in the form of a sign, already contains

the social germ that gives it the possibility of crossing the boundary of the self to the other (PLAZA, 2003, p. 57).

Seu Sami 's plots allow for a relationship with the idea of connection, affective bonds and the human mind (memory), more specifically with neurons. The affective family ties, perhaps the artist portrays when he deals with subjects about *emptiness* , present in his work.

Your Sami surrounds the space in the exhibition space at Museu Vale, covering the walls of the corridors with blankets in *gestural weaves* , lines that connect as if it were a network of interconnected neurons. These blankets literally connected at both ends of the museum provoke a comparative attempt with reception, protection or simply large panels that connect between the space “full of emptiness” through the threads of paper mass composed of experiences and transience.

Seu Sami 's plastic forms and neural networks transcends simply material objectivity, permeating through subjective relationships. The idea of memory, which we work on in this interartistic study, brings the similarity with a neural network, referring beyond the anatomical/image aspects to crossings of a symbolic order, making an interconnection between emptiness, absence and memory. These connections are imagetically related to the absent father and the affective family ties, which through the symbology of the support brings the subjectivity of the senses converted into *paper networks* .

CONCLUSION

We live in a codified world and this imagery territory is present daily. In everything we see there is information, whether in an object or non-object. Depending on what it is, through our translations, they show aesthetic forms and phenomena that go beyond physical characteristics, interconnecting philosophical and poetic concepts and also subjectivities.

The formativity of *something* is not exactly present in the *form* , but goes beyond formic discussions, in a set of ideas that transcend objectivity. These issues are closer to the identity of the subject *who judges them* , as prejudgments are usually interspersed with personal experiences, which arise through linguistic references, which are directly or indirectly interconnected by symbolic intersections, loaded with the existential *self* . Perhaps intersemiotic ideas are more linked to interpersonal translations. Thus, the interartistic studies of the work *Seu Sami* , dialogue with the symbolic aspects “taken” by subjective ideas, but the metalinguistic character is intertwined with the personal experiences of both (artist and

spectator) that translate and materialize its imagery. The intersemiotic hypotheses are the similarity of the representations of what the “eye” and the “spectator” see, what the body felt and the individual experiences translated before the work .

BIBLIOGRAPHIC REFERENCES

AMARAL, Aracy. **Hilal Sami Hilal – Margem Paragem – Landscape Mirage** . São Paulo, 2010. Atlas: Catalog of the exhibition at the Lasar Segall Museum. São Paulo. Official press, 2010.

BERGSON, Henri. **Matter and memory** . 2. Ed. São Paulo: Martins Fontes, 1991.

BORGES, Jorge Luís, **Works Complete** . Sao Paulo: Ed. Emece, 1989.

DIDI-HUBERMAN, Georges. **What we see, what looks at us** . Translated by Paulo Neves. São Paulo, 1998.

FREITAS, Alexandre Siqueira. **Clash Between Forms: Intra and Interart Approaches**. PÓS: Magazine of the Graduate Program in Arts at EBA/UFMG . v.6, n.12: Nov.2016 - Available at <https://eba.ufmg.br/revistapos> . Access: through the author himself.

FOUCAULT, Michael. **This is not a pipe** . Rio de Janeiro: Peace and Land, 1988.

HERKENHOFF, Paulo. Curation and Text. **Your Sami: Hilal Sami Hilal** . São Paulo: Museu Vale/Sesc-Pompéia, 2008.

LACAN, Jacques. **String Wheels** . RJ, 1975.

Lent, Robert. **One Hundred Billion Neurons: fundamental concepts of neuroscience**. Sao Paulo: Ed. Athenaeus, 2004.

MENDES, Neusa. **Gesture and body memory** . In: Hilal Sami Hilal. Victory 2001.

PAREYSON, Luigi. **Aesthetics: theory of formativity**. Translation by: Ephraim Ferreira Alves. Petropolis: Voices, 1996.

PEACE, Octavio. **The Enigma of Languages**. Literary Supplement. São Paulo, 1984.

PLAZA, Julius. **Intersemiotic Translation** . Sao Paulo: Ed. Perspective, 2003.

PEIRCE , C.S. **Semiotics** . São Paulo. Perspective, 1977.

RAMALDES, Maria Aparecida. **The poetics of Hilal Sami Hilal: Pages, books, calligraphic gestures and scriptures**, 2015. Dissertation – Federal University of Espírito Santo, Vitória – ES.

RODRIGUES, Regina. Investigative paths in ceramics. In: CIRILO, José;

GRANDO, Angela (org). **Creation archeology**: studies on the creation process. Belo Horizonte: C/Arte, 2009.

SANTAELLA, L. Dialogism (MM Bakhtin and CS Peirce: similarities and differences) In: **semiotic cruise**. Port: Assoc. Portuguese semiotics, 1985.